

A Study on the Knowledge of Karma-yoga in the Bhgavad Gita and Its Relevance in Modern Day Society

Rashmi Rekha Handique and **Dr. Nabaprasad Nath**

Department of Philosophy, Nowgong College (Autonomous)

Corresponding E-mail : rashmirekhahandique518@gmail.com

The most spiritual and sacred text of Hinduism Srimad Bhgavad Gita is a part of the epic Mahabharata. It is basically a dialogue between Krishna and Arjuna, where Krishna explains the true meaning, motive, duty and actions of our life. It emphasizes the Karma-yoga. We the human being has to do our work, as it were inherent in our existence. And the Gita's advice is that everyone should follow the Niskama karma as the means to achieve goals in our worldly life. It is not renunciation of action but Niskama karma means the action without any desire for result. The action should be selfless and it should be performed for the benefit of others.

The human being by their nature seeks the result of their action. Here question arises if it is possible to practice desire-less action. This paper aims to develop the fundamental teaching of Karma-yoga of the Gita and its relevance in modern day society. It is also a humble attempt to explain modern problems of human life and its possible solutions through the teachings of the Gita.

Keywords: Bhagavad Gita, Karma-yoga, Niskama-karma, Action, Desire, Knowledge.